

Encryption and Decryption Using Hash and Verify

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Abstract- The encryption key is derived from the password in password-based encryption. Most implementations of Password-based Encryption will be supplemented with a randomization technique, known as salt, to make the task of going from keyword to key exceedingly time-consuming for an attacker. Password hashing is a basic method of saving a database's user passwords. Users submit their password, which is then sent through a hash algorithm, which converts it to a fixed-length string of random characters. MD5 and SHA256 are two popular hash functions. When a password is "hashed," it indicates it's been converted into a scrambled version of itself. A user's password is taken, and the hash value is calculated using a defined algorithm from the combination of the password and the key, using a key known to the site. Password verify () checks to see if the hash matches the password. The algorithm, cost, and salt are included in the hash returned by password hash ().As a result, it contains all of the information required to verify the hash. This allows the verify function to validate the hash without requiring a separate stroge for the salt or algorithm. This function is not vulnerable to timing attacks.

Keywords: *Cryptography, Encryption, Decryption, Password Based Encryption, hash, verify.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Technology is progressing at such a breakneck pace these days, it's difficult to keep up.especially while sending a message, but we also do it all the time. make a safety complaint Users place a high value on data security when exchanging data. This necessitates a means for ensuring data integrity throughout data sharing .Many changes and the transmission of data as is the case in data transmission many changes and the transmission of data as is the situation in data transmission many changes and data exchanged by irresponsible parties in order to take action. Cryptography is always linked to data security.

Cryptography is the study of how to protect a message's security and secrecy from irresponsibility by encoding the message into an unreadable form (chipertext). Cryptography is a branch of mathematics that deals with information security issues like confidentiality, data integrity, and authentication. As a result, the data's genuineness may be assured. Cryptography is a branch of mathematics that deals with information security issues like confidentiality, data integrity, and authentication. As

a result, the data's genuineness may be assured. Encryption and decryption are two fundamental cryptography processes that will be addressed in this study. Both procedures encrypt and decrypt using the same key. The same key is used for encrypting and decrypting.. Secret Key is another name for this method. Cryptosystem with a shared key or symmetric key. The encryption procedure makes the message readable (plaintext) but randomly unreadable (chipertext), while a decryption process is the inverse of encryption, transforming chipertext to plaintext of the same key. That use the same key, convert chipertext to plaintext. We'll implement password-based encryption schemes in the encryption and decryption to implement symbolic and computational cryptography using symmetric, asymmetric, and password-based encryption. The usual reported offline attacks might be taken into account in the security procedure because the adversary will go to any length to obtain any information about the credentials used. . As a result, we make no allowances for the potential that the enemy may play a role, with the option of installing a normal active attack and gathering data from contacts with other players. Now is the time to combine these findings with a password-based encryption analysis.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Cryptography

Cryptography is the study and application of secure communication mechanisms in the presence of adversaries, or third parties. It is concerned with the creation and analysis of protocols that prohibit harmful third parties from accessing information shared between two entities, therefore adhering to many principles of information security. A scenario in which a message or data shared between two parties cannot be accessed by a third party is referred to as secure communication. An adversary is a malevolent entity in cryptography that seeks to retrieve valuable information or data by compromising information security principles.

B. Encryption and Decryption

The technique of converting plain text data (plaintext) into something that appears random and meaningless is

known as encryption (cipher text). The process of transforming ciphertext to plaintext is known as decryption. The key that was used to encrypt the data must be used to decrypt a specific piece of ciphertext. The process of encoding data is known as encryption in cryptography. This procedure turns plaintext data into ciphertext data. Only authorised parties should be able to decrypt ciphertext and access the original data. Decryption is the process of restoring encrypted data to its original state. In most cases, it's a reversal of the encryption process. Because decryption requires a secret key or password, it decodes the encrypted information so that only an authorised user can decrypt the data.

The graphic depicts the encryption and decryption processes.

Figure1.Encryption and Decryption Process

C. Cryptography Algorithm

Symmetric encryption uses only one key (a secret key) to encode and decrypt electronic data. To use the key in the decryption process, the entities communicating using symmetric encryption must exchange the key. This encryption method varies from asymmetric encryption, which encrypts and decrypts messages using a pair of keys, one public and one private. Data is changed to a form that no one can understand unless they have the secret key to decrypt it using symmetric encryption methods. The algorithm reverses its operation once the message has been delivered to the intended recipient who has the key, restoring the message to its original and comprehensible state. It could be a specific password/code or a random string of letters or numbers generated using a secure random number generator that both the sender and the recipient utilise (RNG).

Symmetric encryption algorithms are divided into two categories:

Block algorithms. Algorithms that use blocks With the use of a certain secret key, set lengths of bits are encrypted in electronic data blocks. The system retains the data in memory while it is encrypted, waiting for entire blocks.

Stream algorithms. Instead of being stored in the system's memory, data is encrypted as it streams. A stream cypher is an encryption technique that encrypts and decrypts a set quantity of data using a symmetric key. In contrast to an asymmetric cypher key, a symmetric cypher key is an encryption tool that may be used for both encryption and decryption.

Some examples of symmetric encryption algorithms include:

D. AES

The Advanced Encryption Standard (AES), often known as Rijndael, is the most widely used symmetric algorithm. This is the encryption of electronic data standard established by the United States National Institute of Standards and Technology in 2001 and published in US FIPS PUB 197. The DES standard, which had been in use since 1977, has been superseded by this one. The AES encryption has a block size of 128 bits as defined by NIST, but it can have three alternative key lengths, as indicated by AES-128, AES-192, and AES-256.

E. DES

DES was the first standardised cypher for protecting electronic communications in "modern" computing, and it is still in use in various forms today (e.g. 2-key or 3-key 3DES). Because of the processing capacity of modern computers, the original DES is no longer utilised because it is considered "weak."

Symmetric encryption has its own set of disadvantages. Its weakest feature is its essential management components, which include:

F. Key Exhaustion

The symmetry Every usage of a key 'leaks' some information that an attacker may potentially use to recreate the key. The establishment of a key hierarchy to guarantee that master or key-encryption keys are not overused, as well as the proper rotation of keys that do encrypt large amounts of data, are among the defences against this behaviour. Both of these techniques require competent key-management procedures to be traceable, as data may be lost if (for example) a retired encryption key could not be recovered.

G. Attribution data

Symmetric keys, unlike asymmetric (public-key) Certificates, lack embedded metadata such as an expiry date or an Access Control List to indicate the type of use the key can be put to, such as Encrypt but not Decrypt. Standards like ANSI X9-31 address the latter issue by allowing a key to be linked to information that specifies how it should be used. A key-management system, on the other hand, is required for complete control over what a

key can be used for and when it can be used. Key Management at large scale When only a few keys (tens to low hundreds) are involved in a scheme, the management overhead is low and can be handled through manual, human work. With a large estate, however, keeping track of expiration dates and coordinating key rotation rapidly becomes impossible. Consider the following scenario for an EMV payment card deployment: A special provisioning and key-management solution is required for millions of cards multiplied by many keys per card.

H. Asymmetric Algorithms

Asymmetric-key algorithms work similarly to symmetric-key algorithms in that plaintext is coupled with a key, sent through an algorithm, and the result is ciphertext. The sender encrypts the communication with the receiver's public key, leaving only the receiver with his or her own private key to decrypt it. ECC and RSA are two well-known methods that use asymmetric keys. The asymmetric algorithm's process can be watched.

Figure 2. Asymmetric key cryptography

Asymmetric and Symmetric Algorithms are compared:

The merits and disadvantages of both symmetric and asymmetric algorithms are discussed.

Cryptography with an excessive amount of symmetric keys:

1. The symmetric cryptography algorithm is meant to be quick to encrypt and decrypt.
2. The symmetric key is only a few inches in length. To produce a random number, you can use a symmetric approach.
3. To create a stronger encryption, a symmetric key algorithm can be built.

Asymmetric key cryptography has the following advantages:

1. Only private keys must be kept confidential by all communication entities. Symmetric key cryptography eliminates the need to send a private key.
2. Public key pairs do not need to be changed over long periods of time.
3. It's possible to utilise it to deliver symmetric keys.

4. Members on da can be digitally signed using some public key techniques.

I. Cryptography-related attacks

Information drives practically every element of human existence in the modern day, not just business. As a result, it has become critical to safeguard sensitive data from unwanted actions such as cyber-attacks. Consider the various forms of attacks that information is commonly susceptible to. Attacks are usually classified according to the action taken by the attacker. As a result, an attack can be passive or active

J. Passive attack

A passive attack's principal purpose is to gain unauthorised access to information. Intercepting and eavesdropping on a communication channel, for example, can be considered a passive attack. These actions are passive in nature since they have no effect on the information or communication route. A passive attack is frequently mistaken for data theft. The main difference between stealing physical objects and stealing information is that data theft leaves the data in the owner's control. As a result, passive information attack is riskier than stealing items, because information theft may go undiscovered by the owner.

K. Active attack

An active threat entails altering the data in some way by applying a process to it. Consider the following illustration:

1. Making unlawful changes to the information.
2. Initiating an unintentional or unauthorised data transmission.
3. Changing authentication data connected with information, such as the originator's name or the timestamp
4. Unauthorized data deletion.
5. Denying legitimate users access to information (denial of service).

L.Hash Function

A cryptographic hash function is a mathematical process that transforms data of any size into a fixed-size bit array. It's a one-way function, or one that can't be inverted. A cryptographic hash function is an algorithm that receives an arbitrary quantity of data—a credential—and generates a fixed-size output of encrypted text called a hash value, or simply "hash." This encrypted text can then be saved in place of the password and used to validate the user later. Any function that can map data of any size to fixed-size values is referred to as a hash function. Hash values, hash codes, digests, or just plain

hashes are the values returned by a hash function. In most cases, the values are used to index a hash table, which is a fixed-size table.

What a hash cryptography function requires:

1. Enter any number of characters.
2. The output of the result is of a predetermined length.
3. For any value of x , $H(x)$ is simple to calculate.
4. $H(x)$ is a one-way function.
5. $H(x)$ is never in a bad mood around other people.

A hash function turns a numerical input value into another compressed numerical value. The input to the hash function can be any length, but the output is always the same. Message digests, or simply hash values, are the results of a hash algorithm. The hash function is depicted in the diagram below.

M. Hash Functions' Characteristics

The following are some of the most common characteristics of hash functions:

N. Output with a Fixed Length (Hash Value)

1. The hash function converts data of any length to a predetermined length. Hashing the data is a term used to describe this operation.
2. Hash functions are sometimes referred to as compression functions because the hash is usually substantially less than the original data.
3. A digest is also known as a hash since it is a smaller representation of a larger material.
4. An n -bit hash function is a hash function having an output of n bits. Popular hash functions provide values ranging from 160 to 512 bits.

Figure3. hash function

O. Operational Efficiency

1. In general, computing $h(x)$ for any hash function h with input x is a quick procedure.
2. Hash functions are substantially faster than symmetric encryption in terms of computation.
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4. In general, computing $h(x)$ for any hash function h with input x is a quick procedure.
5. Hash functions are substantially faster than symmetric encryption in terms of computation.

P. Password Based Encryption

Password Based Encryption (PBE) is a symmetric cryptographic method that encrypts data using a password-like key and decrypts it with the same key to produce the same data as the plaintext data. PBE (Password-Based Encryption) is a symmetric cryptographic method that encrypts data using a password-like key and decrypts it with the same key. Carry out the decryption procedure in order to obtain the data is same to the plaintext data in plaintext When a cipher text is encrypted, it becomes unreadable .Others have contributed. A password and salt will be mixed to generate random data through the application function procedure, which will then be processed by the iteration count to produce data in the form of chipertext once the mixing process is complete

Q. MD5 (Message Digest 5)

The MD5 message-digest technique, which generates a 128-bit hash value, is a frequently used hash function. Despite the fact that MD5 was created with the intention of being used as a cryptographic hash function, it has been discovered to have numerous flaws. One of the most extensively used one-way hash functions is Message Digest 5 (MD-5). Ron Rivest created MD-5, the fifth hash function. MD-5 is a progression of MD-4 with

the addition of one round. MD-5 divides the input text into 512-bit blocks, which are then broken into 32-bit sub-blocks of 16 pieces. The MD-5 generates four 32-bit blocks, which add up to 128 bits, which is known as the hash value. The main node of MD5 has a 512-bit message block that is divided into four rounds. MD-5 generates a 128-bit output from the lowest byte A to the highest byte D. Each communication will be encrypted, and the number of bits contained in the message will be determined first. As much as b bits is taken into account. Here b is an integer non-negative bit, b can be zero and not necessarily multiples of eight

III. PROBLEM DEFINISION

Through the use of codes, cryptography is an information security method used to safeguard company information and communication against cyber-attacks. Triskele Labs views it as the art of concealing information in order to prevent unauthorised access to your data. Password cracking is the technique of retrieving passwords[1] from data that has been encrypted and stored in or communicated by a computer system in cryptanalysis and computer security. A typical method (brute-force attack) is to repeatedly try password guesses and compare them to a cryptographic hash of the password that is publicly available. [1] Password cracking is the technique of retrieving passwords[2] from data that has been encrypted and stored in or communicated by a computer system in cryptanalysis and computer security. A typical method (brute-force attack) is to repeatedly try password guesses and compare them to a cryptographic hash of the password that is publicly available. [3]

IV. RESULT

The method of converting data into another form or code so that access to the data is confined to only those with the correct decryption key is known as password encryption. Encrypted data, often known as ciphertext, is one of the most common and widely used types of data security. Even if you have a data breach involving cipher text, the attackers will not be able to read the information. Encryption protects your online privacy by converting personal information into “for your eyes only” messages that are only seen by those who need them – and no one else. You should ensure that your emails are sent over an encrypted connection or that each communication is encrypted. Encryption protects data sent, received, and stored on a device. Text messages on your smartphone, jogging records on your fitness watch, and financial information received through your online account are all examples of this. As a result, it contains all of the information required to verify the hash. This allows the verify function to validate the hash without requiring a separate stroge for the salt or algorithm. This function is not vulnerable to timing attacks. Password encryption is the mechanisms to protect all data in system or site. Protecting the all things in the website.

V. CONCLUSION

Finally, cryptography has the potential to do social harm. Governments are worried that encryption will make it more difficult to meet law enforcement and national security aims. Terrorists, for example, may use encryption to send material over the Internet, which law enforcement agencies would be unable to decrypt. Hash and verify functions used to protect and encrypt the password and decrypt the data

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